

Procedural generation of biomorphic structures using a specialized programming language

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Abstract. This paper presents a method for the procedural generation of fractal trees based on the use of cubic splines and a variable-thickness brush drawing algorithm. Unlike classical approaches where objects are constructed from linear segments, the proposed method ensures high visual quality due to the seamless connection of branches at bifurcation nodes. The mechanism for dynamic control of line thickness and transparency along the spline trajectory is described, guaranteeing natural smoothness and volume of the graphic structures. The implementation of the method using a specialized programming language allows for the efficient description of complex recursive processes and the creation of detailed objects, while minimizing the code complexity. Simulation results confirm that this approach provides fast generation of diverse tree forms that possess a realistic appearance and are characterized by a high degree of uniqueness.

Keywords: fractal trees, L-systems, procedural generation, splines, recursion, brush drawing.

INTRODUCTION

Modern computer graphics and virtual environments [1] require efficient methods for reproducing complex natural objects [2], where the key factor is the balance between generation speed and visualization realism. Aristid Lindenmayer's L-systems are considered a traditional tool for modeling vegetation [3]. However, classical approaches based on strict geometric recursion often lead to visual monotony: branches appear as a set of linear segments, and noticeable geometric defects occur at the bifurcation nodes [4].

To overcome these shortcomings, this paper proposes an approach based on abandoning traditional linear primitives in favor of nonlinear geometry, which paves the way for creating realistic natural forms [5].

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The proposed approach is based on the technique of drawing splines with a variable-thickness brush. The core idea lies in abandoning the geometric rectilinearity characteristic of classical L-systems. To achieve this, the trajectory of each individual branch is described by a parametric cubic Bézier curve [6], which allows for the replacement of straight segments with smooth, volumetric structures.

Mathematically, the branch segment model is defined by four control points P_0, P_1, P_2, P_3 according to the formula:

$$B(t) = (1-t)^3 \cdot P_0 + 3 \cdot (1-t)^2 \cdot t \cdot P_1 + 3 \cdot (1-t) \cdot t^2 \cdot P_2 + t^3 \cdot P_3 \quad (1)$$

where $t \in [0,1]$ is a parameter that determines the position of a point on the curve; P_0 and P_3 define the start and end of the branch, while control points P_1 and P_2 shape its curvature.

Unlike standard approaches, this model employs the principle of drawing with a variable-thickness brush. The visualization of the branch occurs through iterative movement along the spline trajectory, where graphic primitives are applied at each point $B(t)$. The thickness of these primitives changes dynamically depending on the value of the parameter t . This approach (Fig. 1) allows for the formation of a cohesive visual silhouette with a natural change in thickness that mimics an organic form.

Fig. 1. Stages of organic branch visualization: (a) base curve, (b) stroke primitive overlay, (c) final form.

An important condition for the visual correctness of the model is the smoothness of transitions at the branch bifurcation nodes. This principle is demonstrated by the example of connecting three splines (Fig. 2). The seamlessness of the joint is achieved because all segments share a common connection point, and the adjacent control points are located symmetrically relative to this node (Fig. 2a). Such symmetry ensures that the curvature of each branch at the contact point remains identical, which eliminates the appearance of sharp angles. As a result, when transitioning to variable-thickness splines, the outlines of

the lines merge into a single, cohesive, and harmonic form, avoiding gaps or overlapping graphic elements (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 2. Modeling of a bifurcation node: (a) point symmetry diagram, (b) connection result.

PROCEDURAL GENERATION ALGORITHM

The process of constructing a fractal tree begins with the initialization of global parameters that define the overall appearance of the future structure. To achieve this, variables controlling the scale, branch tilt angles, trunk thickness, and the level of randomness (entropy) are defined using a specialized programming language. Tree generation is activated by calling a rendering function, which sets the initial growth point and the tree's orientation.

The program code for initializing and launching the fractal tree generation is provided below:

Listing 1. Parameter initialization and fractal tree rendering

```
W = 800    \ Screen width
H = 600    \ Screen height
thk = 20   \ Trunk thickness (1..50)
ang = 40   \ Branch tilt (10..60)
ent = 8    \ Entropy (1..20)
crv = 0.1  \ Curvature (0..0.3)
scale = 1  \ Scale
branch(1, W/2, H*0.85, -pi/2, 0, 0, thk, 1)
```

The practical implementation of the method is based on the recursive function branch. Its task is to build an individual branch and initiate the growth of subsequent ones. The function calculates the endpoint of the current branch and its curvature to ensure a smooth transition to the next bifurcations. A key feature is that each branch passes information about its tilt and thickness to its "descendants" as inherited parameters. This allows the tree to appear as a cohesive structure rather than a set of fragmented segments:

Listing 2. Recursive function for fractal tree rendering

```
function branch(d,x,y,a,dx,dy,w,o: float) {
  if (d > 12) return

  \ Calculate branch length
  L = 100 * $scale / d + random(-$ent, $ent)

  \ Calculate curve points
  ex = x + cos(a) * L
  ey = y + sin(a) * L
  cx1 = x + dx
  cy1 = y + dy
  cx2 = x + cos(a)*L*0.7 + random(-L,L)*$crv
  cy2 = y + sin(a)*L*0.7 + random(-L,L)*$crv

  \ Render the curve
  w1 = w * 0.6
  o1 = pow(o) * 0.999
```

```
curve(x,y,cx1,cy1,cx2,cy2,ex,ey,w,w1,o,o1)

\ Calculate control point increments
nx = ex - cx2
ny = ey - cy2

\ Calculate branch angles
a1 = a - random(10, $ang) * pi/180
a2 = a + random(10, $ang) * pi/180

\ Render the next two branches
branch(d+1, ex, ey, a1, nx, ny, w1, o1)
branch(d+1, ex, ey, a2, nx, ny, w1, o1)
}
```

The "curve" function plays a specific role in this process. Although its internal source code is not provided here, it is responsible for the visual implementation of the proposed method. Its primary purpose is the rendering of a cubic spline with dynamic thickness (w , $w1$) and opacity (o , $o1$) parameters along the entire trajectory. Based on the calculated curvature, the function performs drawing with a variable-thickness brush [7], the parameters of which change smoothly from the start of the branch to its end. This achieves an effect of natural softness and ensures the seamless connection of tree elements with one another.

SIMULATION RESULTS

Practical testing of the developed method has confirmed its ability to generate complex natural forms with a high degree of visual fidelity. The visualization results demonstrate the main advantage of this approach: the absence of geometric gaps at the nodes, which is typically a critical issue for the linear models of classical L-systems.

Fig. 3 presents the final model of a detailed tree. Due to the iterative brush drawing along the spline trajectories, the trunk and branches acquire smooth contours.

Fig. 3. Image of a fractal tree constructed using the recursive method

To verify the flexibility of the algorithm, a series of tree procedural generations were performed with different input parameters for entropy, tilt, and curvature. Fig. 4 presents eight variations of trees obtained using a single recursive function.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a method for the procedural generation of fractal trees that allows for a departure from linear-segment models in favor of natural organic forms. The main result of the research is the development of an algorithm that combines the mathematical precision of cubic splines with a variable-thickness brush drawing technique. This approach has completely eliminated the problem of geometric gaps at bifurcation nodes, ensuring continuity and smooth transitions between tree elements.

The use of a brush with variable thickness and transparency parameters along the spline trajectory provides objects with natural volume, bringing the digital model as close as possible to a real biological prototype. At the same time, the implementation of the algorithm using a specialized programming language has proven its efficiency, allowing for the description of complex recursive processes [9] with concise code without losing object detail.

The proposed approach provides the necessary balance between visualization quality and generation speed, which is of practical importance for the development of virtual worlds [10], game engines, and landscape modeling systems. The obtained results demonstrate that combining algorithmic recursion with non-linear visualization methods allows for the creation of digital objects that are structurally as close as possible to their natural counterparts.

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Fig. 4. Variability of procedurally generated fractal trees

These examples demonstrate that changing only a few basic numerical values [8] allows for a wide variety of tree forms to be obtained. At the same time, each individual variation maintains the integrity of contours and natural softness of lines. Thus, the simulation results confirm the effectiveness of combining spline mathematics with the variable-thickness brush drawing technique for creating natural plant forms.